

SSLN countries completing PSAT by KP sub-population pillar

KP sub-population pillar	Countries completing PSAT / countries with structured programmes
Sex workers	15 / 15
Men who have sex with men	14 / 15
People who inject drugs	10 / 15
People in prisons and closed settings	9 / 10
Trans and gender-diverse people	7 / 10

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